

Research Article

Wetlands importance for the waterfowl species (order Anseriformes) wintering in Bulgaria, based on the Mid-Winter Waterbird Census data

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Abstract

The main approach for the conservation of wintering waterbirds is through the identification of wintering sites, the assessment of their abundance and the determination of wintering population trends. The target sites are set for the implementation of management measures for both wintering species populations and sites falling within the Natura 2000 National Ecological Network. The aim of the present study is to identify the most important waterbodies in the country, based on data from the mid-winter waterbird census during the period 1977–2021. The assessment covers 75 waterbodies falling within the following five area categories used in the MWWC—the Danube River, the North Black Sea Coast, the South Black Sea Coast, natural and artificial waterbodies in North and South Bulgaria. The assessment was made from the analysis of data on 32 species of waterfowl birds, which were split into two groups—24 common species occurring in winter (with numbers over 500 individuals recorded during the study period) and eight rare species (with total numbers less than 500 individuals). The results show that the wetlands along the Black Sea Coast, the big inland reservoirs and the Danube River are the regions most frequently inhabited by wintering waterfowl, holding the highest abundance and number of species. Conservation value indices were calculated for each site, as well as biodiversity indices like the Shannon-Winner and Simpson indices, which identified which wetlands are of greatest the importance for the protected, rare and dominant waterbird species.

Key words: Biodiversity indices, conservation value, species diversity, waterfowl, wintering sites assessment

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1. Introduction

Conservation of the wintering bird populations requires an integrated approach that includes protection of their habitats, monitoring of their status, preventing conflicts with human activities such as hunting and pollution, and raising public awareness of the importance of these species. The main approach for the conservation of wintering waterbirds is through the identification of wintering sites, the assessment of their abundance and the determination of wintering population trends (Wetlands International 2018).

In Bulgaria the Mid-Winter Waterbird Census (MWWC) is one of the oldest schemes for bird monitoring that was first implemented at a national level, it has been applied since 1977. It includes over 360 wetlands, natural and artificial reservoirs and sectors along the major Bulgarian rivers, including the Danube, and along the entire Bulgarian Black Sea Coast. There are several studies which analyzed the population trend of waterfowl species during the winter, as well as their wintering sites—both at a national or regional level (Kostadinova and Dereliev 2001; Michev et al. 1991; Michev and Profirov 2003; Nankinov et al. 2004; Dimitrov et al. 2005). Data from the MWWC are published in the annual national reports for the state of the environment.

Biodiversity conservation requires the availability of a large range of data on species distribution and abundance. In order to effectively manage the sites inhabited by wintering birds, it is necessary to periodically assess the status of birds and the status of wetlands. As information on wintering birds increases, methods for assessing wintering populations have been improved. This makes it possible to assess the effectiveness of different management measures in protected areas or protected zones (Burfield et al. 2023). The International Waterbird Census is one of the largest citizen science biodiversity monitoring schemes in Europe, having operated since 1967. This long-term dataset provides a good basis for assessing the effectiveness of the EU Birds Directive and other EU policies in conserving waterbirds that winter in significant numbers in the European Union (Wetlands International 2015). Up-to-date information on the distribution and status of wintering birds is published on the Wetlands International website (Wetlands International 2025).

The present study is an extension of the studies on wintering waterbirds conducted in Bulgaria. It is also a continuation in the designation of Spatial Protection Areas within the Natura 2000 network in Bulgaria (Kostadinova and Gramatikov 2007). A key tool in making policy decisions for the conservation of migratory and wintering waterfowl is to identify those geographic areas or wetlands that support the greatest numbers of wintering waterfowl during the adverse winter months. Changes in climatic conditions are a key factor in the distribution of waterbirds. Monitoring of waterfowls at their wintering sites could measure the effectiveness of Important Bird Areas (IBAs) of Protected areas or Natura 2000 sites as an important network for their protection (Pavón-Jordán et al. 2020). The main objective of this study is to assess the value of wetlands using different parameters, such as species composition, conservation value and biodiversity indices. The assessment is based on analyses of monitoring of the wintering waterbirds of the order Anseriformes and their wintering sites over a period of 45 years (1977–2021). Our study will contribute to a better understanding of the ecological requirements of wintering waterbirds, their diversity, and the conservation activities to be taken for the most important wetlands in Bulgaria.

2. Data and methods

Mid-winter counts of wintering waterbirds have been continuously implemented in Bulgaria since 1977, with the number of participants, new wetlands monitored and data increasing each year. Since 2007, it has been part of the monitoring methodologies of the National Biodiversity Monitoring System (NBMS

2016) administered by the Executive Environment Agency (EEA). Based on this information, reports on wintering waterbirds are prepared following the requirements of the International Mid-Winter Waterbird Census (MWWC) and Article 12 of the Birds Directive. This study is based on data provided by Wetlands International (IWC) reported by Bulgarian officials and data published in the National Environmental Report. The scope of the analysis includes all species of the order Anseriformes recorded in the period of 45 years—from 1977 to 2021.

In order to identify the most important wetlands and wintering sites of the waterfowl species, we applied the following approach. All data from all known relevant sources were combined into a single database containing the following information: species list, numbers by year, visited sites or sectors with geographical information—centroid of waterbodies or mean of the sector lengths.

A total of 32 species of wintering birds of the order Anseriformes were recorded in Bulgaria during the period 1977–2021. Species with more than 500 individuals recorded for the whole period were classified as numerous, 24 in total. Species with records of up to 500 individuals (in total) were classified as rare bird species, 8 in total. To determine which wetlands are most valuable for the numerous species, for each site we summed up the number of individuals for each species. Sites holding the highest abundance for a given species were considered most valuable for that numerous species. Some of the species are widely distributed and occur in almost every wintering site, hence we assumed a statistical sample size threshold of 90% of the wintering population for the numerous species. For each species, sites are ranked in descending order until 90% of wintering individuals are reached during the study period. Rare waterbirds are very scarce. It is therefore necessary to identify all areas where they winter as important for their wintering population.

For each site, the following parameters were used—number of species and individuals for each of the above-mentioned two groups of birds, and the number of species and individuals of all waterbird species of the order Anseriformes.

According to their geographical location, all sites were assigned to five main area categories used in the MWWC—Danube River, North Black Sea Coast, South Black Sea Coast, North Bulgaria and South Bulgaria (Fig. 1). According to their watertype and size, we classified all waterbodies and sectors into six groups:

A—Freshwater and saltwater lakes and reservoirs along the Black Sea Coast: ten sites (three of them along the North and seven along the South Black Sea Coast) with a total area of about 15704 ha.

B—The Black Sea itself, coastal sectors: nine coastal sites (three along the North and six along the South Black Sea Coast).

C—Large inland reservoirs: 25 sites, totalling about 46243 ha in area.

D—Danube River and adjacent wetlands: seven sites, totalling about 13773 ha in area.

E—(other) Rivers: seven sites or river sectors, totalling about 1890 ha in area.

F—Small inland reservoirs and waterbodies: 17 sites—six of them are in North and eleven are in South Bulgaria, totalling about 1795 ha in area.

Categories B and F were defined according to the conditions at Article 141a of the Bulgarian Act on Waters (MRDPW 2022).

Figure 1. Five main area categories used in the MWWC and the most important site classified into six groups (A–F) according to their type, size and location. The system of wetlands coding is presented in Suppl. material 1.

The conservation significance of each site was determined based on modified conservation value index according to Scarton (2017). Affiliation of the identified bird species to three legally recognised documents was made: The Bulgarian Biological Diversity Act (Annex II and Annex III) (MOEW 2022), Bulgarian Red Data Book (Golemansky 2015), Species of European Conservation Concern (SPEC) and the waterfowl species from the Birds Directive 2009/147 (Annex I) (EP and Council of EU 2009). For each site, the number of bird species from these documents has been calculated for 2021. Thus, the year of 2021 was chosen as a starting point also for the calculation of the Conservation Value Index (CVI) for wintering waterfowl as we referred to the last published European Red list of birds (Birdlife International 2022). CVI was calculated for each wetland monitored in 2021 (the last year of study) using the formula (eq. 1):

$$CVI = n / N \quad (1)$$

Where: n is the number of species with conservation value, and N is the total number of species.

According to the CVI value, we defined a rating scale to identify the significance of wetlands: weakly significant sites with CVI = 0–0.32, moderately significant CVI = 0.33–0.66 and highly significant sites with CVI = 0.67–1.00.

For each site, the two main indices for biodiversity assessment were calculated: the Shannon-Winner index (H) and the Simpson index (D). For their

calculation, all observed species of waterbirds of the order Anseriformes were used, as well as their total number of individuals. The calculations were made using the statistical software PAST 4.15. The map was produced using QGIS desktop ver. 3.22.12.

3. Results

3.1. Waterfowl abundance

Summarized information on the waterfowl abundance, their wintering sites and their conservation value are presented in Table 1 for species with total numbers over 500 individuals, Table 2 for the rare species, as well as in Suppl. material 1.

For the whole study period, the largest number of wintering birds was recorded in the area of Shabla Lake Complex, with 2613538 individuals. It is followed

Table 1. Numerous species of the order Anseriformes (more than 500 ind. in total, during the period 1977–2021), their total abundance, the total number of wintering sites, abundance in the most important wintering sites and the corresponding number of wintering sites and their conservation value. The “conservation value” parameter per species is indicated either as present (+) or absent (-). The “recorded in 2021” parameter indicates whether the species is present (+) or absent (-) in that year.

N	Numerous waterfowl species	Total counts / Total sites	90% Winter population / sites	Conservation value / recorded in 2021
1	Greater White-fronted Goose (<i>Anser albifrons</i>)	5434611 / 104	4937881 / 9	- / +
2	Mallard (<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>)	2495424 / 294	2271837 / 30	- / +
3	Common Pochard (<i>Aythya ferina</i>)	685801 / 111	656482 / 12	+ / +
4	Red-breasted Goose (<i>Branta ruficollis</i>)	559674 / 28	531080 / 3	+ / +
5	Tufted Duck (<i>Aythya fuligula</i>)	256516 / 70	233614 / 28	- / +
6	Common Teal (<i>Anas crecca</i>)	179137 / 188	161343 / 29	- / +
7	Common Shelduck (<i>Tadorna tadorna</i>)	110526 / 104	102676 / 2	+ / +
8	Eurasian Wigeon (<i>Mareca penelope</i>)	95165 / 123	85144 / 41	- / +
9	Northern Shoveler (<i>Spatula clypeata</i>)	74373 / 63	69039 / 3	- / +
10	Mute Swan (<i>Cygnus olor</i>)	46235 / 155	41741 / 30	+ / +
11	Northern Pintail (<i>Anas acuta</i>)	24113 / 67	22059 / 22	- / +
12	Greylag Goose (<i>Anser anser</i>)	19797 / 43	17263 / 8	+ / +
13	Red-breasted Merganser (<i>Mergus serrator</i>)	18629 / 39	16833 / 12	+ / +
14	Tundra Swan (<i>Cygnus cygnus</i>)	13977 / 75	12612 / 18	+ / +
15	Gadwall (<i>Mareca strepera</i>)	8238 / 91	7524 / 22	+ / +
16	Smew (<i>Mergellus albellus</i>)	7750 / 64	6981 / 16	+ / +
17	White-headed Duck (<i>Oxyura leucocephala</i>)	6127 / 10	6086 / 4	+ / +
18	Common Goldeneye (<i>Bucephala clangula</i>)	4937 / 50	4424 / 16	+ / +
19	Red-crested Pochard (<i>Netta rufina</i>)	4357 / 44	3886 / 19	+ / +
20	Goosander (<i>Mergus merganser</i>)	822 / 42	751 / 17	+ / +
21	Whooper Swan (<i>Cygnus columbianus</i>)	696 / 16	660 / 6	+ / +
22	Greater Scaup (<i>Aythya marila</i>)	640 / 24	583 / 10	+ / +
23	Garganey (<i>Spatula querquedula</i>)	583 / 7	550 / 2	+ / -
24	Ruddy Shelduck (<i>Tadorna ferruginea</i>)	578 / 33	520 / 9	+ / +

Table 2. Rare waterfowl species (less than 500 ind. in total, during the period 1977–2021, the total number of wintering sites and their conservation value. The “conservation value” parameter per species is indicated either as present (+) or absent (-). The “recorded in 2021” parameter indicates whether the species is present (+) or absent (-) in that year.

N	Rare waterfowl species	Total counts / Total sites	Conservation value / recorded in 2021
1	Ferruginous Duck (<i>Aythya nyroca</i>)	402 / 39	+ / +
2	Common Eider (<i>Somateria mollissima</i>)	130 / 14	+ / +
3	Velvet Scoter (<i>Melanitta fusca</i>)	111 / 18	+ / -
4	Long-tailed Duck (<i>Clangula hyemalis</i>)	106 / 8	+ / -
5	Bean Goose (<i>Anser fabalis</i>)	74 / 10	+ / -
6	Common Scoter (<i>Melanitta nigra</i>)	64 / 10	+ / -
7	Lesser White-fronted Goose (<i>Anser erythropus</i>)	10 / 7	+ / -
8	Barnacle Goose (<i>Branta leucopsis</i>)	2 / 2	+ / -

by the Durankulak and Vaya Lake complexes, with over one million birds each. Of all 32 species recorded, the most abundant was the Greater White-fronted Goose, accounting for more than 54% of all wintering birds. The main wintering sites of the species are the North and South Black Sea Coast, with the largest numbers of individuals found in the area of Shabla, Durankuvak and Vaya. The second most abundant species was the Mallard, with 24.4% of all observed birds. Species on the other end with numbers exceeding 1 % are Red-breasted Goose with 558946 ind. (5.64 %), Tufted Duck with 255559 ind. (2.58%), Common Teal with 171806 ind. (1.73 %), Common Shelduck with 109883 ind. (1.11%) and Eurasian Wigeon with 93612 ind. (~ 1%). All other species are less than 1% of the total observed wintering individuals.

In terms of rare bird species, the most abundant species is the Ferruginous Duck (*Aythya nyroca*) which has been recorded in all five main geographic regions, but in very low numbers (1 to 49 individuals per count), 402 individuals in total for the whole period. Rare species such as the Long-tailed Duck (*Clangula hyemalis*) and the two species of the genus *Melanitta* are below the threshold of 100 individuals.

3.2. Wintering sites location

Each of the five regions (Fig. 2) has different number of wetlands or sectors which depends on their geographical position. The number of wintering sites is highest in South Bulgaria, while the highest wintering numbers have been recorded along the Black Sea Coast.

Depending on the type of wetlands, their origin and size, the results for the observed wintering waterfowl at the monitoring sites for the whole period (1977–2021) are grouped as follows:

- A–Lakes and reservoirs along the Black Sea Coast

All 32 waterfowl species have been found to winter at these wetlands, in total over 63.75% of all individuals recorded. Six species had numbers exceeding 10000 wintering individuals for the whole period—*Anser albifrons* (3877694 ind.), *Anas platyrhynchos* (706174 ind.), *Aythya ferina* (599414 ind.), *Branta ruficollis* (534469 ind.), *Aythya fuligula* (215490 ind.), and *Tadorna tadorna* (106645 ind.).

Figure 2. Number of wintering sites or sectors (dark grey) and percentage of recorded waterfowl individuals per region (white).

- B–Black Sea Coast sectors

The dominant species were *Anser albifrons* with 368352 birds observed and four other species *Aythya ferina* (62824 ind.), *Anas platyrhynchos* (53039 ind.), *Aythya fuligula* (27937 ind.), *Branta ruficollis* (21802 ind.), had numbers exceeding 10000 individuals for the study period. Black Sea hosted a total of 5.62% of the wintering birds recorded. Four species were never observed in the sea itself: *Oxyura leucocephala*, *Spatula querquedula*, *Anser erythropus*, and *Branta leucopsis*.

- C–Large inland reservoirs

In terms of number of wintering species and number of wintering individuals, they ranked second out of all significant sites, with a total of 2045782 (20.63%) individuals of 30 species. Long-tailed Duck and Lesser White-fronted Goose have not been recorded. The most abundant species were *Anas platyrhynchos* (983040 ind.) and *Anser albifrons* (892156 ind.). The following species had more than 10000 recorded individuals: *Anas crecca* (73938 ind.), *Aythya ferina* (40279 ind.), and *Mareca penelope* (31754 ind.).

- D–Danube River and adjacent wetlands

They include important wetlands such as Srebarna Lake, Kalimok-Brashlen complex, Orsoya and Mechka fishponds, Peschina and Malak Preslavets marshes, river islands etc. All sections of the Danube from the village of Vrav to the town of Silistra are important wintering areas for waterfowl (Fig. 1). A total of 26 wintering species have been recorded, 9.2 % (910543 ind.) in numbers. Among the rare species recorded were *Aythya marila*, *Cygnus columbianus*, *Aythya nyroca*, *Clangula hyemalis*, *Melanitta fusca* and *Anser erythropus*. The Mallard and Greater White-fronted Goose were found to be the most common wintering waterbirds in the Danube River with 621201 and 217005 wintering individuals counted for the period respectively.

- E–Rivers

There are five inland rivers which were found to be important wintering sites for waterfowl birds—Vit, Maritsa, Tundzha, Arda and Yantra. Tundzha and Maritsa rivers are the longest and they have been reported to IWC into two parts each. They host a smaller number of waterbirds species—22 in total, with just 0.4 % in numbers. Among the most common species preferring these sites are *Anas*

platyrhynchos, *Anser albifrons*, *Anas crecca*, *Cygnus olor* and *Aythya ferina*. The Mallard is the most common and numerous wintering species with 26866 ind.

- F–Small inland reservoirs and waterbodies

A total of 28 species have been recorded, with just 0.37 % (37026 ind.) in numbers. Nevertheless, some sites have been found to host rare species like *Melanitta fusca* (Dabnika and Telish reservoirs), *Cygnus columbianus* (Trastikovo reservoir), *Aythya marila* (Trastikovo reservoir), *Anser fabalis* (Dabnika reservoir), *Oxyura leucocephala* (Trastikovo reservoir), and *Melanitta nigra* (Pet mogili quarry), *Anser erythropus* (Tyurkmen reservoir). The Mallard is, again, the most common and numerous species with 27923 individuals observed.

3.3. Waterfowl species richness

In terms of species diversity, the most significant wintering sites for waterfowl birds are the salt and brackish marsh complexes along the North and South Black Sea Coast. The largest number of species has been recorded in the complex of the Burgas lakes–Mandra, Vaya, Atanasovsko and Pomorie lakes, as well as along the North Black Sea Coast–Durankulak and Shabla Lake complexes. The richest part along the Danube River is the section between the village of Somovit and the town of Ruse, with a total of 23 species of waterfowl recorded. Inland, the largest number of species was found at the Studen Klad-

Figure 3. Species richness and numbers of the waterfowl recorded at their wintering sites in Bulgaria between 1977 and 2021. The numbers denote the 75 sites presented in Suppl. material 1.

enets, Pyasachnik and Ovcharitsa reservoirs, where 22 species were recorded for the whole study period. Species richness and bird numbers for all sites are presented in Fig. 3.

3.4. Conservation value

As for 2021 data, 18 out of the 32 waterfowl species have conservation status and another seven are game species. Regarding the wintering site importance for species of conservation value, a great diversity is observed (Suppl. material 1). According to the adopted rating scale, seven sites are of high conservation value (CVI > 0.67), 46 sites are of moderate conservation value, 16 sites were of weak significance and seven sites were not visited in 2021. The wetlands with the highest score (CVI = 1) for the 2021 year were the Tyurkmen reservoir and the "Dalyana-Vlas" sector of the South Black Sea Coast, followed by the Trastikovo reservoir (CVI = 0.78) and the Malko Sharkovo reservoir (CVI = 0.75).

3.5. Biodiversity indices

In terms of the two biodiversity indices, the highest values were found in the waterbodies and sectors along the South Black Sea Coast, with the Pomorie Lake complex (H = 2.10; D = 0.84) and Atanasovsko Lake (H = 1.94; D = 0.81) having the highest scores. This makes these two sites most valuable both for rare and numerous wintering waterfowl species.

4. Discussion

Bulgaria is situated in the Western Palearctic biogeographic realm. The country falls in the so-called Black Sea/Mediterranean flyway zone (Wetlands International 2012), thus being in the middle of a big geographical crossroad, indicated by a high species diversity and a bulk of important sites as wintering places.

The summarized MWWC data for the period 1977–1981 by Michev et al. (1983) in Bulgaria show that the most important sites of international significance are nine wetlands—Srebarna Lake, Shabla-Ezeretz Lake complex, Durankulak complex, Ovcharitsa reservoir, Persina – iztok marsh, Atanasovsko Lake, Vaya Lake and Mandra complex, as well as Malko Sharkovo reservoir. According to Dimitrov et al. (2005) the wintering waterfowl at the Burgas lakes (Pomorie, Atanasovsko, Vaya lakes and Manda complex) during the period 1996–2022 were found to be most numerous in January and February—a total of 32000 birds recorded, the bulk of which (186448 ind.) being concentrated in Mandra and Vaya. Contrary to the results received by these authors, that Pomorie Lake complex holds the least species diversity among all Bourgas lakes and wetlands complex, we found maximum value of the Shannon and Simpson biodiversity indices for this site during the wintering season. This makes Pomorie Lake complex, together with Atanasovsko Lake, one of the most important sites for wintering waterfowl. According to our analyses, the sites at the Black Sea Coast and nearby lake complexes and reservoirs are the most important for wintering waterfowl species in Bulgaria.

Nankinov et al. (2004) identified the most important sites for 26 species of waterfowl on the wetlands around the city of Sofia, indicating that 24.2% of the

autumn migrants stayed to winter. Our analyses show that the sites located in the Sofia region are less important compared to those along the Black Sea regions but when assuming its geographical position—high fields surrounded by mountains, they provide quite good conditions for wintering waterbirds. Michev and Stoyneva (2007) presented a red list of wetlands of greatest importance for biodiversity conservation, which includes extinct wetlands as well as the critically endangered and data-deficient wetlands. According to their analyses, Mandra, Ovcharitsa and Pyasachnik reservoirs cover the criteria for future Ramsar sites.

In Bulgaria, waterbird abundance was higher inside the IBAs, legally protected or not. The estimation of conservation value for wintering sites showed that 25 of the sites are Natura 2000 / IBAs sites or protected areas. The remaining sites have the potential to become an IBA because they hosted rare species or are important place for some of the numerous waterfowl species. It is necessary for all wintering sites to have yearly monitoring with continuous observations in order to get more data regarding the status of the species and to possibly envisage future site protection. Among the main habitat variables that influence the appearance of waterbirds were found to be water depth (Bolduc and Afton 2008), water level fluctuation, salinity, topography, food accessibility, wetland size and connectivity, which serve as main factors for the waterbirds spatial distribution (Ma et al. 2010). According to Cerda-Peña and Rau (2023), based on assessment of more than 40 studies, the area (size) of the wetlands is one of the most important habitat variables for species-richness relationships (in 70% of the cases). For restoration and conservation purposes other variables must be included, such as habitat heterogeneity and species abundance which influence the number of species. Another important variable for species distribution and estimation of their trends is temperature anomaly. Pavón-Jordán et al. (2019) estimated that waterbird abundance was positively correlated with temperature anomaly, with this pattern being strongest towards north and east Europe. Water temperature as an environmental variable was found to explain the richness of waterbird species (Yetis et al. 2021) in inland wetlands and marshes. At low air temperatures (below 0 °C), waterbirds have greater abundance and species composition at sites that are less pressured by extreme winter conditions and are characterized by the presence of permanent and non-freezing water, warmer winter temperatures and concentrations of several wetlands, so-called cold refugee winter sites (Adam et al. 2015; Musilová et al. 2015). The European wintering distribution of waterfowl has shifted north-eastward, most likely in response to changes in temperature in recent decades and their numbers increased in inland Europe (Lehikoinen et al. 2013; Adam et al. 2015). Pavón-Jordán et al. (2020) found that the species using shallow water, deep-water and farmland habitats have a different response to winter conditions (level of North Atlantic Oscillation index (NAO)) and main driving force is finding suitable sites for foraging in winter months. In warmer and milder winters (high NAO index), birds inhabiting shallow waters have a shifted centre of distribution to the northeast. Whereas in species that feed mainly on fish and inhabit deep waters, the shift to the northeast is associated with deterioration of environmental conditions and significantly cold winters (mean or low NAO index).

The species richness and diversity of birds depend on the presence of a large landscape diversity—the presence of shrubs, forests, agricultural lands

and even a nearby urban environment. This provides a large amount of organic matter, which favours a good breeding ground for waterfowl (Elliott et al. 2020). They also depend on the interaction between wetland surface area and distance to the nearest wetland (Hamza et al. 2024).

The results of the present study show that wintering waterfowl birds mainly concentrate along the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast, where large saltwater and freshwater lakes, the Black Sea itself and large areas of agricultural land provide suitable conditions for the birds to feed and rest. The large inland reservoirs are second in importance for the wintering waterbirds—Studen Kladenets, Zhrebchevo, Rozov Kladenets and Pyasachnik being of significant importance among them. In Western Bulgaria, which has a pronounced continental climate, the Iskar and Ogosta reservoirs are of the greatest importance for the waterfowl. The Danube River is the third most important site, where birds find suitable conditions for feeding. The small reservoirs and other rivers are still insufficiently studied, however they often provide suitable conditions for some wintering rare species of waterfowl.

5. Conclusion

The main factors influencing the distribution and abundance of waterfowl birds were found to be the geographical location of the wintering sites, as well as the food availability—the large lakes, reservoirs and the Black Sea coastal area provide diverse feeding conditions for all species of waterfowl. The wetlands with the highest biodiversity index values are the large lake complexes along the Black Sea Coast—Pomorie, Atanasovsko, Vaya, Mandra, Shabla and Durankulak. The Srebarna Nature Reserve at the Danube River and the Black Sea Coast between the Kamchia River and Cape Emine also have high biodiversity index values. Inland wetlands with high index values are Sopot and Rozov Kladenets reservoirs. These wetlands with large open water areas provide favourable conditions for wintering waterfowl species because they are less likely to freeze in cold winters and it is easier for the birds to avoid disturbance. The results show that the protection or species-specific management of these sites would contribute to the better protection of the wintering waterfowl populations. Further research is needed on the influence of climatic and environmental factors on the distribution, species composition and diversity of waterfowl during the winter months.

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Additional information

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No conflict of interest was declared.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: RHS. Data curation: BN. Supervision: BN. Visualization: RHS. Writing - original draft: RHS. Writing - review and editing: BN.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

Supplementary material 1

The most important wintering sites for waterfowl species in the period 1977–2021

Authors: Radoslav Stanchev, Boris Nikolov

Data type: pdf

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